

Original Research Article

Predictive value of hematologic and coagulation parameters in assessment of severity and evolution of COVID-19 patients

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Abstract

The new disease COVID-19 was recently diagnosed because of many cases of pneumonia with unknown etiology. The pathogenic agent is a betacoronavirus: severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). This virus causes an excessive immune response in the host called a “cytokine storm,” followed by extensive tissue damage, dysfunctional coagulation, and thrombotic complications. Patients with COVID-19 can be asymptomatic or have mild or severe symptoms. In some cases, COVID-19 worsens very rapidly; initially being asymptomatic or showing only mild symptoms, patients may quickly need intensive care to help them with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), septic shock, and/or multiple organ failure. COVID-19 thrombosis, an early complication, could be diagnosed at the time of hospitalization or within 24 hours after hospitalization. Evaluation of ferritin, interleukin 6 (IL-6), troponin I, and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) with D dimer provides more information on the severity of COVID-19. In such a condition, we need to evaluate several criteria to make a rapid diagnosis and to prescribe appropriate treatment. In our study, we observed that medical history, including cardiovascular diseases, thrombosis, and obesity, was important in evaluating COVID-19 patients. The combination of old age (over 65 years) and a history of thrombosis was also a significant predictor of a fatal outcome. The use of a predictive venous thromboembolism (VTE) scale, such as the Geneva risk score for VTE or the Padua prediction score for VTE risk, was important in identifying groups at risk of thrombotic complications. The neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), ferritin, C reactive protein (CRP), and LDH were general model matching statistics for independent variables that predicted a fatal outcome in COVID-19 patients. Moreover, COVID-19 patients who at the onset presented with pneumonia had a higher NLR than patients without pneumonia. The presence of D-dimers was strongly correlated with CRP and procalcitonin. Deficiency in protein S was probably important in a cytokine storm, as patients with a low level of protein S had a high level of IL-6. These preliminary results need to be validated by a larger cohort as well as by comparative data obtained during patients’ follow-up.

Keywords: COVID-19, Neutrophil-Lymphocytes Ratio, D-Dimers, Protein S, Pneumonia

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INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 was recently discovered (December 2019/January 2020) due to many cases of pneumonia with unknown aetiology in Wuhan China. The pathogenic agent is an ARN enveloped severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) (Mittal et al., 2020).

SARS-CoV is involved in an excessive immune response in the host “cytokine storm”, followed by extensive tissue damage, dysfunctional coagulation and thrombotic complication. The main role in the immune reaction is IL-6 activity with the both pro and anti-inflammatory effect. The cytokine release syndrome is characterized by fever and multiple organ dysfunctions (Song et al., 2020; Ye et al., 2020).

There are risk factors described by some studies including older age, male gender, co-morbidities: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.3%), hypertension (16.9%), diabetes (1.8%), coronary atherosclerotic heart disease (1.9%), cerebrovascular diseases (8.2%) hepatitis B and liver cirrhosis (1.5%) (Guan et al., 2020). Oncological diseases are an important risk factor for the severe evolution of COVID-19. This risk increases due myelosuppressive effects of treatment and the presence of neoplasia COVID-19 infection in itself causes lymphopenia which could be more severe due to the chemotherapy administration, resulting higher mortality rates (Guan et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2020). Obesity is also a risk factor for severe COVID-19 infection and high mortality rate; these type of patients frequently present pneumonia and need mechanical ventilation in intensive care units (Albashir, 2020; Sanchis-Gomar et al., 2020). Patients with COVID-19 may be asymptomatic or have various symptoms. Patients frequently experience fever, fatigue, dry cough, headaches, and myalgia. Digestive symptoms: diarrhea - the most frequent digestive symptom, nausea, decreased appetite, vomiting, abdominal pain may be diagnosed at the onset or in evolution of COVID-19, after the onset of respiratory symptoms (Zaim et al., 2020; Pascarella et al., 2020). Fever (98.6%), fatigue (69.6%), dry cough and diarrhea are more frequently diagnosed. The following are less frequently reported: muscle ache, confusion, headache, sore throat, rhinorrhoea, chest pain, sputum production, nausea and vomiting. Sometimes patients have a severe form of COVID-19 with severe respiratory failure, sepsis, septic shock, and multiple organ dysfunction syndromes (MODS) (Wong et al., 2020).

The evolution of the disease is very fast, the average time from its first symptom to dyspnea being 5.0 days and to ARDS was 8.0 days (Wang et al., 2020). COVID-19 complications are ARDS, acute myocardial injury, anemia, liver, testicular or kidney injury, septic shock and/or multiple organ failure, refractory metabolic acidosis, coagulation disorder (Temgoua et al., 2020; Peng et al., 2020; Eddy et al., 2020).

Venous thromboembolism, stroke, myocardial infarction are frequently reported and have been diagnosed in severely ill patients, several of whom are hospitalized in the intensive care unit (ICU) (Bray et al., 2020; Lodigiani et al., 2020; Klok et al., 2020). D-dimer is an important marker in the evaluation of patients with COVID-19. A severe inflammatory response accompanied by a secondary hypercoagulable state should be a possible cause of increases of D Dimer. Sometimes during the evolution of COVID-19 D-dimer continues to increase meaning that the disease progresses and reflects a prognostic indicator of mortality (Jean and Jerrold, 2020; Pedro et al., 2020). The evaluation disease severity showed 4 categories: mild, moderate, severe, and critical disease. The mild group includes patients with minimal symptoms without pulmonary involvement on chest radiography or CT scan. The moderate form of COVID-19 is characterised by interstitial changes in chest imaging without dyspnea (respiratory rate >30 breaths per minute) pulse oximetry oxygen saturation at rest \leq 93%; or arterial blood oxygen partial pressure/oxygen concentration \leq 300 mmHg (1 mmHg=0.133 kPa). The significant progression (>50%) in lesions in 24–48 h; sequential assessment of organic failure assessment (SOFA) of \geq 2 points; pneumothorax and/or other clinical conditions requiring hospitalization are characteristic for severe COVID-19 disease. Patients with critical illness are patients with respiratory failure who require mechanical ventilation; septic shock; additional organ failure (Clinical management of COVID-19, 2020).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The main objective of our study is to evaluate haematological, coagulation and biochemistry parameters to identify predictive parameters associated with critical illness and poor prognosis. The secondary objective is to assess the presence of the correlation between these identified parameters and the thrombotic complication during the evolution of COVID-19. This observational study (retrospective and prospective) included all COVID-19 patients hospitalised in 4 Departments of Colentina Clinical Hospital Bucharest (Hematology, Pneumology, Neurosurgery and Intensive Care Unit-1) in April - August 2020. The approval of the Hospital Ethical Committee was obtained prior to starting this study. All 268 patients enrolled in the study were confirmed with COVID-19 by real-time reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test for nasal and pharyngeal swab samples. The data on demographic, basic clinical, laboratory and imaging characteristics and particularities of evolution was obtained from the hard copy and electronic medical records from each Department involved in the study, by

maintaining personal data confidentiality.

The study group was divided into two groups depending on the type of medical care required - medical care (non-ICU group) and intensive care (ICU group). All patients were staged according to clinical examination and the results of CT scan and laboratory investigation. Characteristics of patients group are represented in Table 1

Statistical analyses

We performed Chi-square tests to assess differences in demographic and clinical/ laboratory data between ICU and non-ICU groups. Correlations between clinical parameters (medical history, symptoms at onset and laboratory values at onset) and fatal outcome or the presence of complications/ severe disease stage in patients with COVID-19 were made using multivariate logistic analysis. Statistical analyses for difference between at least two of the assessed subgroups were performed by using the Kruskal Wallis test. The rank test was used to correlate between two variables. In all these tests we obtained p value that was considered statistically significant for $p < 0.5$. Sensibility and specificity of one of predictive VTE scales used in the study were performed using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis in the thrombosis/non thrombosis group to evaluate the accuracy of predictive factors for these scales to have caused thrombotic complications in patients with COVID-19. All statistical analyses were performed by using MedCalc Statistical Software version 16.4.3 (MedCalc Software be, Ostend, Belgium; <https://www.medcalc.org>; 2016

RESULTS

The types of symptoms and the presence of complications are important in assessing the severe evolution of COVID-19 patients, chi-squared=62.08, $p < 0.0001$. The symptoms presented at onset were classified in 4 groups. Groups 1 included all patients with upper respiratory symptoms +/- fever, group 2, associated dyspnea, cough, group 3 patients with digestive symptoms (diarrhea, nausea, loss of appetite, abdominal pain), group 4 patients presented simultaneously respiratory and digestive symptoms or presented the neurological involvement (seizures, headache, hemiplegia, neurological coma, etc.). Patients admitted to intensive care units (ICU) showed severe symptoms - dyspnea, asthenia, neurological symptoms including neurological coma, these types of symptoms covering more than 50% of the group of patients. Table 1

During evolution patients with COVID-19 had complications: infections 13.8%, thrombosis (stroke, myocardial infarction, deep venous thrombosis or

pulmonary embolism) 20.1%, other complications (hepatitis, renal failure etc.) 10.8%. A good evolution with the absence of any complication was observed in 55, 2%. The frequency of complications during evolution of COVID – 19 was higher in the ICU patients compared with non-ICU patients who in most cases, did not have any complications (Table 1). Using the WHO recommendation, we classified COVID-19 into 3 stages: stage 1 without pneumonia, stage 2 with mild /moderate pneumonia, stage 3 including patients with severe pneumonia associated with various grades of hypoxia. The patients admitted to the ICU Department presented severe forms of pneumonia; some patients had a bad evolution with the increase of the lung lesions highlighted on CT scan. We did not do this evaluation for all patients due severe evolution of the disease (Table 1).

We also analysed the predictive role of various comorbidities (cardiovascular diseases, thrombosis, obesity – body mass index (BMI) > 25) presented in patients with COVID-19 as independent variables and fatal outcome as a dependent value, the chi-squared obtained was 48.90, $p < 0.001$. In this model previous thrombosis and obesity appear to be important in evaluating the outcome of patients with COVID-19 (statistically significant Wald was for obesity = 17.17, $p < 0.0001$ and previous thrombosis=13.95, $p = 0.0002$). Odds ratio (OR) in patients with COVID-19 with a history of thrombosis was 4.05 (95% CI: 1.95-8.46), and for obesity 3.76 (95% CI: 2.01–7.05) means that medical history including cardiovascular diseases, thrombosis and obesity is important for evaluation in patients COVID-19. The association between age (older than 65) and a history of thrombosis is also a significant predictor of fatal outcome, OR 3.24 (95% CI: 0.99-10.59), $p = 0.039$.

To identify risk groups for thrombotic complication we used 2 predictive VTE scale Geneva risk scores for VTE and Padua prediction score for risk of VTE. We evaluated the specificity and sensitivity of these 2 scales. The Geneva risk score for VTE has the specificity 71.35, the sensitivity 85.11, and ass. criterion >5 Figure 1. The Padua prediction score for risk of VTE has the specificity of 85.42, the sensitivity 68.09, ass. criterion >6. Figure 2.

The model that used these scales as predictive variables for evaluating the fatal outcome is statistically significant; chi-squared=112.81, $p < 0.0001$. These two scales predict the result in 81.2% of the cases. The Wald value for the Padua prediction score for VTE risk was 4.52, $p = 0.03$; OR = 1.42 (95%CI: 1.03-1.96), for the Geneva risk score for VTE Wald value was 3.61, $p = 0.06$; OR = 1.39 (95%CI: 0.99-1.94).

The median value of D-Dimers was 0.95 (0.27-20). D Dimers are strongly correlated with CRP value, rho 0.53 (0.44-0.61), $p < 0.0001$, and procalcitonin value, rho 0.613 (0.533-0.68), $p < 0.0001$. The disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) scoring system proposed by ISTH was used to identify DIC in our cohort of patients. A few patients (4%) had this score more than 5 fit for DIC

Table 1. Characteristic of COVID-19 patients groups

Characteristics		Non-ICU patients (166 patients)	ICU patients (102 patients)	P value	
Age		53 (min 17, max 92)	67 (min 34, max 94)	< 0,000001	
Male (%)		54.82	48.03	0.49	
Hospitalization (days)		14 (min 1, max 57)	9 (min 1, max 89)	0,006	
Symptoms (at the onset)	Asymptomatic (%)	30.12	11.76	0,0006	
	Respiratory (cough, dyspnoea, odynophagia) (%)	58.43	67.65	0.13	
	Digestive (diarheea, abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting) (%)	7.23	5.88	0.67	
	Simultaneously respiratory and digestive symptoms or Neurological symptoms (hemiplegia, seizures, cefalea, neurological coma) (%)	4.22	14.71	0.02	
Stage of COVID-19	Stage 1 (%)	32.53	4.9	< 0,0001	
	Stage2 (%)	51.2	23.53	< 0,0001	
	Stage3 (%)	16.27	71.57	< 0,0001	
Pneumonia diagnosed by CT scan	Absence (%)	31.33	7.84	< 0,0001	
	Unknown (%)	16.87	13.73	0.49	
	0-25% (%)	17.47	9.8	0.08	
	26-50% (%)	15.66	8.82	0.1	
	>50% (%)	18.67	59.8	< 0,0001	
Complications	Absence (%)	85.54	5.88	< 0,0001	
	Infectious (%)	2.41	32.36	< 0,0001	
	Thrombosis (%)	9.64	37.25	< 0,0001	
	Other (%)	2.41	24.51	< 0,0001	
Medical History	Ischemic heart disease (%)	9.72	32.22	< 0,0001	
	Arterial hypertension (%)	36.11	54.44	0.006	
	Heart failure (%)	2.77	22.22	< 0,0001	
	Thrombosis (stroke, myocardial infarction, pulmonary embolia, deep venous thrombosis) (%)	4.16	28.88	< 0,0001	
	Stroke (%)	1.38	17.77	< 0,0001	
	Diabetes mellitus (%)	19.44	34.44	0.01	
	Obesity (%)	27.08	24.44	0.65	
	Dyslipidaemia (%)	30.76	17.77	0.02	
	Neoplasia	Haematological neoplasia (%)	14.58	6.66	0.06
		Solid tumors (%)	11.11	16.66	0.22
	Pulmonary diseases (%)	13.19	14.44	0.78	
	Chronic liver diseases (%)	11.11	17.77	0.15	
	Renal Failure (%)	11.80	18.88	0.13	
Autoimmune diseases (%)	9.72	7.77	0.61		
Body-mass index (kg/m ²)		32.14 (min 20.06, max 47.75)	28.2 (min 14.66, max 48.8)	0.1	
WBC (x 10 ⁹ /L)		7.08 (min 0.92, max 364.92)	8.92 (min 1.1, max 346.11)	0.01	
Lymphocyte (x 10 ⁹ /L)		1.53 (min 0.2, max 254.35)	0.86 (min 0.04, max 297.64)	< 0,000001	
Neutrophils (x 10 ⁹ /L)		4.41 (min 0.02, max 88.89)	7.09 (min 0.57, max 25.52)	0,000002	
Neutrophils– Lymphocyte ratio (NLR)		2.55 (min 0.01, max 63.96)	8.28 (min 0.02, max 90.04)	< 0,000001	
Hb (g/dl)		13.2 (min 5.3, max 17.2)	12.6 (min 4.4, max 17.3)	0.02	

Table 1. Continue

Platelet (x 10 ⁹ /L)	229.5 (min 6, max 498)	192 (min 20, max 658)	0.08
IL6 (pg/ml)	28.14 (min 1.5, max 465.3)	57.61 (min 1.69, max 2505)	0.003
CRP (mg/dl)	12.63 (min 0.14, max 333.7)	80.1 (min 1.35, max 386.5)	< 0,000001
Procalcitonin (mg/dl)	0.06 (min 0.02, max 9.53)	0.34 (min 0.03, max 784)	< 0,000001
LDH (U/L)	232 (min 113, max 2432)	459 (min 150, max 2024)	<0,000001
Ferritin (ng/ml)	353 (min 18.8, max 52778)	866 (min 50.39, max 23436)	< 0,000001
AST (UI/L)	24.35 (min 8.3, max 468)	54.7 (min 2.1, max 2589.7)	< 0,000001
ALT (UI/L)	23.7 (min 4.3, max 224.6)	34.4 (min 3.1, max 1152)	0,003
Colesterol (mg/dl)	155.2 (min 48.5, max 274.4)	127.4 (min 29.8, max 271.7)	0,01
PT (sec)	13.8 (min 11.6, max 100.8)	15.4 (min 12.1, max 115.2)	< 0,000001
INR	1.02 (min 0.86, max 7.89)	1.14 (min 0.89, max 9.05)	< 0,000001
PTT (sec)	29.05 (min 21, max 80.2)	30.75 (min 20.4, max 74.6)	0.001
D Dimer (ug/ml FEU)	0.62 (min 0.1, max 20)	2.57 (min 0.33, max 20)	< 0,000001
CK (UI/l)	75 (min 12, max 1235)	174.5 (min 7.27, max 4897)	< 0,000001
CK-MB (UI/l)	17.4 (min 8.5, max 144.5)	26.9 (min 10.1, max 600.3)	< 0,000001
Pro-BNP (pg/ml)	120 (min 5, max 53793)	854.5 (min 13.26, max 70000)	< 0,000001
Troponin (pg/ml)	8.77 (min 3.68, max 178.4)	27.74 (min 0.12, max 4897)	< 0,000001
Cardiolipinici Antibodies IgG (MLP)	5.12 (min1.69, max18.53)	12.95 (min4.44, max46.64)	0.09
Cardiolipinici Antibodies IgM (MLP)	11.27 (min7.72, max 21.33)	11 (min 5.97, max 105.52)	0.95
Antirombin III (%)	99 (min 61, max 123)	97 (min 7.22, max 199)	0.4
Protein S (%)	60 (min18, max 102)	42.5 (min 8, max 80)	0.005
Protein C (%)	99 (min 55, max 200)	77.5 (min 15, max 170)	0.001
Lupus anticoagulant	1.43 (min 1.15, max 7.19)	1.37 (min 0.76, max 1.86)	0.23
APACHE Score		25.79+/-7.97	
SOFA Score		7.68+/-4.96	

Figure 1. ROC evaluation for Geneva risk score for VTE risk in patients COVID-19 enrolled

Figure 2. ROC evaluation for Padua prediction score for risk of VTE in COVID-19 patients groups enrolled

diagnosis, all patients belonging to the ICU-group. The Kruskal Wallis test indicated significant differences between S protein and D-Dimers in ICU and non-ICU groups. The logic multivariate analyses did not identify any predictive value of D-Dimers or S protein for the association of thrombosis in patients with COVID-19, although there were significant differences between thrombosis and non-thrombosis group for D-Dimers (non-thrombosis 0.84, min 0.1, max >20; thrombosis group 2.58, min 0.31, max >20), $p=0.000006$; S protein (median value non thrombosis group 56, min 18, max 144; thrombosis group 43.5, min 8, max 102), $p=0.05$; C

protein (non-thrombosis group 94.5, min 16, max 200; thrombosis group 71, min 15, max 169), $p=0.03$. The level of D-Dimers and protein S, protein C could be influenced by a different intensity of inflammation in COVID-19. We obtained significant differences between IL-6 level in COVID-19 groups divided into the normal or abnormal range of protein S but not for D-Dimers or protein C. The median value of IL-6 COVID-19 associated with protein S deficiency was 59.7, min 6.12, max 887.9; in COVID -19 patients with normal value of protein S the level of IL-6 was 27.52, min 1.5, max 999.5; $bp=0.0009$. This result confirmed the influence of

Figure 3. Correlation of median value neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio with duration of ICU hospitalization

Figure 4. Evaluation of AUC corresponding to Neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio median value

inflammation in decreasing value of protein S.

Beta 2 microglobulin is increased in chronic inflammation regulated by interferons and proinflammatory cytokines. High levels of beta-2 microglobulin are present in diseases with a high cell turnover such as multiple myeloma or chronic lymphocytic leukemia/ some types of lymphomas or in viral infection-HIV, CMV and immune diseases. In our study cohort the Beta 2 microglobulin was significantly higher in the ICU group compared with the non-ICU group, $p=0.01$. (non-ICU 2.61, min 1.6, max 3.34; ICU 3.65, min 1.23, max 20.82), $p=0.01$. The explanation could be the involvement of lymphocytes in COVID-19 pathogenesis.

The median value of the neutrophils lymphocytes ratio was 4.06 (95% of median: 3.42-5.29). We set a cut-off

5.29, the values above 5.29 are considered high values. The NLR is significantly higher in the ICU group of patients with COVID-19 than in the non-ICU groups (Table 1). A correlation rank test revealed a slight positive correlation between the level of interleukin-6 (IL-6) and NLR with statistical significance, $\rho=0.242$ (95% CI: 0.02-0.44), $p=0.03$ this ratio seems to be a predictive marker for severe evolution of COVID-19, OR =3.08 (95%CI=1.27-7.47), $p=0.01$. Patients with COVID-19 admitted in ICU had a higher OR - 6.05(95% CI=0.53-68.70)) than OR of non-ICU patients – 2.78 (95% CI=1.07-7.22). NLR, ferritin, C reactive protein (CRP) and LDH are general model matching statistics for independent variables that predict fatal outcome in the group of patients with COVID-19, Chi-squared 62.68,

$p < 0.0001$. Wald statistic for independent variables is: NLR 6.23, $p = 0.01$; CRP 10.75, $p = 0.001$; Ferritin 0.28, $p = 0.59$; LDH 8.58, $p < 0.000$, in this study the proposed model predicts the result in 76.19% of the cases. NLR is much easier to obtain than IL-6 assessment that takes time to perform and could provide valuable information at the time of hospitalization to prescribe appropriate treatment for each patient. In the second stage we analysed the median value (rata overall curve) of NLR for each patient who has more than 1 measurement of NLR. This result was significantly higher in ICU patients than non-ICU (median value NLR: ICU 72.15, min 7.93, max 2185.6; non-ICU 5.7, min 0.2, max 89.04). There is a high correlation between NLR level and the duration of ICU hospitalization, $\rho = 0.76$ (95% CI 0.638-0.845), $p < 0.0001$. Figure 3

Assessing the importance of this factor for admission to ICU of patients with COVID-19 we applied ROC analyses, and the result indicated a high specificity and sensibility of this factor in evaluating the severity of the disease- AUC 0.91 (95% CI: 0,828 - 0,970), $P < 0.001$; sensitivity 91.67, specificity 82.35. Figure 4

Patients with dyspnea, asthenia, confusion, neurological symptoms, association of respiratory and digestive symptoms have $NLR > 50$ compared to asymptomatic or to mild symptoms (no symptoms 3.19, min 0.33, max 44.36; mild symptoms 11.39, min 0.2, max 256.72; severe symptoms 71.94, min 2.31, max 544.65), $p = 0.000001$. Moreover, patients with COVID-19 who evaluated at the onset pneumonia have a higher NLR value than patients without pneumonia (COVID-19 patients +pneumonia 44.36, min 0.2, max 2185; COVID-19 patients-pneumonia 6.3, min 1.21, max 488.921), $p = 0.006$.

DISCUSSION

COVID-19 worsens very rapidly in some cases; there are asymptomatic or mild symptoms and in short time patients need intensive care to help with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), septic shock, and/or multiple organ failure. Some patients have a low severity of pneumonia, but after a few days they develop a severe form and mechanical ventilation becomes an emerging attitude. In this case, we need to evaluate some criteria in order to have rapid diagnosis and to prescribe appropriate treatment. The main goal is to prevent disease progression and reduce mortality (Feng et al., 2020). We identified some comorbidities (obesity, cardiovascular disease, and thrombosis), older age as risk factors for severe evolution. The use of the predictive scale for thrombosis is important in the evaluation of the patient with COVID- to provide correct prophylaxis of thrombotic complication.

Many researchers have identified NLR as a predictive factor for an early-stage of COVID-19 for patients who

are likely to develop a severe form of the disease (Ciccullo et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020). The NLR cut-off is between 3 and 6 (3.04 (Zhang et al. 2020); 3.13 (Liu et al. 2020b); 3.3 (Yang et al. 2020); 5.0 (Liu et al. 2020d); 5.5 (Qin et al. 2020) to 5.87 (Song et al. 2020)), the value above the limit was considered to indicate unfavourable evolution. It was also identified that $NLR \geq 2.973$ (HR = 2.64, 95% CI: 1.42–4.91, $P = 0.002$) as an independent risk factor for progression of COVID-19 (Kerboua, 2020). This marker was considered as a new marker of systemic inflammatory response; patients with COVID-19 with high value of NLR and age ≥ 50 are associated with critical form (Feng et al., 2020). Many centres considered the NLR as a marker for the unfavourable evolution of COVID-19 which was obtained very easily and quickly (Ciccullo et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020; Nalbant et al., 2020; Abigail and Amit, 2020). The NLR value was higher in ICU patients compared to non-ICU patients. NLR in combination with higher levels of inflammatory cytokines, chemokines have been correlated with disease severity. The High level of IL-6 associated with CRP was reported by Zhu et al. as risk factors for COVID-19 (Feng et al., 2020). We obtained a high correlation between the level of NLR and the duration of ICU hospitalization in intensive care. Patients with severe symptoms of COVID-19 have $NLR > 50$ compared with asymptomatic or patients with mild symptoms. The Severity of onset pneumonia is associated with a higher NLR value.

A model of temporal lymphocytes predicting the progression of COVID-19, has been proposed by Li Tan et al. Patients with $lym\% > 20\%$ are recovering while patients with $lym\% < 5\%$ need intensive care (Tan et al, 2020).

It is also important to calculate the NLR as it provides a good characterization of level of inflammation. Inflammation in COVID-19 could be investigated by a panel of analyses that include D-Dimers, serum ferritin, CRP and IL-6. CRP and IL-6 levels have a variable correlation with NLR and have been associated with hospitalization days and unfavourable course of COVID-19 pneumonia. The evaluation of the NLR level could be a guide for indicating specific treatments as Tocilizumab or Eculizumab due to their action as cytokine blockers (Kerboua, 2020). Preliminary data showed that early administration of Tocilizumab following corticotherapy was indicated as having an important role in prevention of cytokine storm and reducing of mortality in COVID-19 (Campins et al., 2020). Based on the predictive value of age-NLR association, 4 risk categories have been proposed: elderly patients, high NLR are included in high risk. These patients should be carefully observed, and the probability for needing intensive care resources is great. Young patients and low tNLR are at low risk and should be treated in a community hospital or at home. Elderly patients with low NLR belong to a moderate risk group and need supportive care and careful monitoring of

vital signs. Young patients with high NLR are at low risk and the treatment is the same as of the young patients with NLR (Liu et al., 2020). Many studies have shown that older age, a delayed care, comorbidities, high levels of pro-inflammatory cytokine, high levels of LDH, procalcitonin and D-dimer are risk factors for adverse outcome (Wang et al., 2020). The cytokine storm is aggravated by the decrease in the number of T cells count during the evolution of COVID-19 and this situation has been associated with a high level of NLR (Liu et al., 2020). We found an association between low level of protein S and high level of IL-6 but we need to include more patients to verify the importance of this finding. COVID-19 is associated with high risk of thrombosis, Bilaloglu found 16% risk of thrombotic event occurrence, much higher than another viral infection like influenza (Bilaloglu et al., 2020).

The explanation could be cytokine storm, hypoxia, endothelial dysfunction, hypercoagulopathy associated or not with platelet hyperactivity (Bilaloglu et al., 2020). Comorbidities, age, male, genders, obesity, cancer, admission to intensive care have been reported as additional risk factors for venous thromboembolism (Khan et al., 2020). In our study we applied the Padua Prediction Score. More than 40% (42,19%) patients included are at increased risk of thrombosis. This result is much higher than Xu study with 16.67% of patients at risk (Khan et al., 2020). This difference could be explained by the nature of our hospital in this pandemic as a support hospital, and the fact that our patients have many comorbidities associated COVID-19. Active thrombosis (pulmonary thromboembolism, stroke, myocardial infarction and deep venous thrombosis) was present in 5.91% of patients with COVID 19, this result is explained by the prophylaxis of thrombosis which was started when the patient was admitted in to our hospital. Another report from China Padua model identified that 40% of patients hospitalized with COVID-19 had a high risk of VTE (Bikdeli et al., 2020). Monitoring of platelet count, PT, aPTT, D-dimer and fibrinogen is mandatory for patients with COVID-19, ASH considering D-dimer as a marker of COVID-19 severity (Bikdeli et al., 2020). Myocardial infarction and stroke seems to be more common in patients with a history of MI or stroke in their medical history (Khan et al., 2020). In our study we identified 8 patients (2,98%) with repeated thrombotic complications (ischemic stroke, myocardial infarction or PE) but in our study group we did not include patients from Neurology or Cardiology.

Stratifying risk of COVID-19 thrombosis seems to be an emergent attitude when prescribing the treatment. Elderly patients with comorbidities, high D-dimer score, high chest score (computed tomography) and high NLR/PLR values, high ferritin, PAI-1, and IL-6 had a high risk of developing thrombosis during the evolution of COVID-19 (Ahmed et al., 2020). Zhang reported in patients with COVID-19 high D-Dimer level (100%),

prolonged prothrombin time (73.7%) and hyperfibrinogenemia (73.7%) and low level of protein C, protein S and antithrombin (Zhang et al., 2020). D-Dimer level is high in patients with COVID-19 and this finding could be explained by the effects of infection on coagulation in infectious disease. D-Dimers level is influenced by inflammation and reflects intra-vascular thrombosis (Price et al., 2020). Moreover, the hypercoagulable condition characterised by increased D-Dimers in patients with pneumonia has been associated with the presence of thrombosis. Patients with COVID-19 showed in their evolution the microthrombosis of peripheral blood vessels. The high level of D-Dimers could be explained by inflammation, disseminated intravascular coagulation, advanced age or infection. VTE should be considered in COVID 19 if the patient has had disproportionately high levels of D-dimer compared to the inflammatory condition (Yu et al., 2020; Tal et al., 2020). A low D-dimer level is important for the exclusion of DVT in patients with COVID-19 (Tal et al., 2020). The high level of D-Dimer at the onset (more than 0.73mg/l) or especially the increase in D-Dimers more than 3.78mg/l are predictive of adverse outcome and high risk of death due thrombotic complications (microthrombosis, pulmonary embolism, acute myocardial infarction, stroke). The presence of thrombosis worsens the evolution of COVID-19 caused by refractory hypoxemia, respiratory failure, disseminated intravascular coagulation or death. In COVID-19 Huertas et al identified endotheliitis affecting several organ systems as the main factor involved in the pathogenesis of COVID-19 pneumonia.

The thrombosis mechanism present in COVID-19 probably involved infection/inflammation, elevated levels of CRP, fibrinogen and IL-6. High thrombin and fibrin production is a consequence of abnormalities of coagulation cascade and tissue factor production. Fibrinolysis is reduced due to the increased production of PAI1 secondary inflammation process. Many pathogenic mechanisms of thrombosis have been described in patients with COVID 19 involving the deposition of complement system components, neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs), high circulating levels of cell-free DNA and histones, deep hypoxemia that causes vasoconstriction, inflammation and thrombosis (Price et al., 2020). There was identified a significant correlation between higher levels of D-dimer and thrombotic complication of COVID-19. Moreover, free protein S levels were found below the normal range without any correlation. The protein S deficiency found in our cohort is probably due to inflammation, virus interaction and pathophysiology of acute lung injury. Its role in macrophage receptor binding (TAM – Tyro3, Axl and Mer) was reported to be involved in hemostasis (Reyes et al., 2020). Thrombosis and disseminated intravascular clotting present in SARS-CoV-2 infection induced depletion of free circulating soluble coagulation protein due to the consumption process in the growing clot. In this process there is also

the depletion of the anticoagulant, protein S. Activated Protein S and C induced the degradation of factor Va and VIIIa. Protein S is also involved in immune hyper-reaction due to its role as in activating ligands for the TAM family of receptor tyrosine kinases. After activation of MER in immune cells the cytokines that are released by these cells in response to SARS-CoV-2 infection are inhibited. The low level of protein S is associated with chronic immune hyperactivation (Lemke and Silverman, 2020). Protein S deficiency and high level of D-Dimers were present in patients with COVID-19 especially in patients with thrombotic complication. In our cohort we obtained a lower level of protein S in patients with thrombosis history compared to patients without thrombotic complication. Protein C level although significantly different, was in the normal range. Although we did not obtain any statistical difference in CRP or ferritin between the COVID-19 group with normal range of protein S and the group of patients with protein S deficiency we did not exclude an influence of inflammation in this observed decrease. Furthermore, IL-6 level was higher in patients with COVID-19 with protein S deficiency; median value of IL-6 in COVID-19 associated with protein S deficiency 59.7, min 6.12, max 887.9 vs. the value of IL-6 in patients with COVID -19 with normal range of protein S 27.52, min 1.5, max 999.5; $p=0.0009$. We did not rule out the hereditary deficiency of protein S in our cohort; it will be necessary to be evaluated in the next follows up. Severe form of COVID-19 present high level of beta-2 microglobulin this inflammation marker seems to be an important marker for COVID-19 evolution and probably would have the same importance in treatment assessment as its importance in HIV infection management (Topçiu-Shufta et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

The association between age (over 65 years) and a history of thrombosis is also a significant predictor for fatal outcome. The NLR, ferritin, C reactive protein (CRP) and LDH are general model matching statistics for independent variables that predict fatal outcome in the group of COVID-19. NLR use is very important; this is quickly obtained and predicts severe evolution of COVID-19. Deficiency in protein S is probably important in cytokine storms, patients with low levels of protein S have a high level of IL-6. We need to expand our study to include more patients and new information should be obtained in the follow up of our patients admitted in order to include data without the active influence of the infection.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank all medical teams from Colentina Clinical Hospital and Matei Bals Institute who

give us interdisciplinary help for patients admitted in our Departments. We thank Professor Rodica Pop and Prof Magda Crinu for the critical review of the manuscript.

Contributions

All authors equally contributed to data by collecting and analysing data, manuscript writing, manuscript reviewing and by researching references. We confirm that this work is original and has not been published elsewhere, nor is it currently under consideration for publication elsewhere.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no potential conflict of interests.

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